

Drwencke, Adcock, and Tucker “*Wound healing and pain sensitivity following caustic paste disbudding in dairy calves*”

Supplemental Figure S1. An example of an adult lactating cow on a commercial farm with horn regrowth on her left side. This cow was not part of our study but serves as an example of horn regrowth. In our experiment, most calves did not experience any horn regrowth, but 30% of paste disbudded horn buds re-grew to a lesser degree than pictured here.

Supplemental Table S1. Model outputs and test statistics for analyses of mechanical nociceptive thresholds (MNT) and average daily gain (ADG).

ADG wk 1-6		ANOVA (Type III SS)				
Variable	DF*	chisq	p-value	N	Conditional R2	Marginal R2
Treatment	1	0.0195	0.89	33	0.22	0.22
Week	1	30.5329	< 0.01			
Breed	1	0.0602	0.81			
Treatment:Week	1	0.1143	0.74			
Treatment:Breed	1	0.0311	0.86			
Week:Breed	1	1.2542	0.26			
Treatment:Week:Breed	1	0.0205	0.89			

Horn bud MNT		ANOVA (Type III SS)				
Variable	DF*	chisq	p-value	N	Conditional R2	Marginal R2
Treatment	1	5.9248	0.01	33	0.1	0.04
Side	1	0.0264	0.87			
Spot	3	1.3912	0.71			
Week	1	1.7384	0.19			
Treatment:Week	1	0.4458	0.50			

Flank MNT		ANOVA (Type III SS)				
Variable	DF*	chisq	p-value	N	Conditional R2	Marginal R2
Treatment	1	0.0926	0.76	33	0.132	0.006
Week	1	0.6828	0.41			
Treatment:Week	1	0.4878	0.48			

*Numerator DF obtained from the Anova type III SS are presented; denominator DF are known to be erroneous in many mixed models and are not presented (e.g. <https://stat.ethz.ch/pipermail/r-help/2006-May/094765.html>).

Variable	Control (n = 15)	Paste (n = 17)	Unpaired T-test		
	Raw average (SE)	Raw average (SE)	95% CI	t-value	p-value
Weaning ADG (kg/d)	0.75 (0.07)	0.61 (0.05)	[-0.33, 0.05]	-1.44	0.16

MNT of each tissue type vs healed	Paired T-test					Min	Max	Mean	Number of hornbuds
	DF	t- value	p-value	95% CI					
Attached Necrotic	11	-0.96	0.35	[-0.710, 0.279]	1.03	3.10	1.51	12	
Detaching Necrotic	16	-2.24	0.03	[-0.303, -0.008]	0.88	1.43	1.10	17	
Exudate	5	-0.16	0.87	[-0.204, 0.179]	0.99	1.30	1.14	6	
Granulation	16	-2.71	0.01	[-0.337, -0.041]	0.85	1.31	1.07	17	
Crust	15	2.74	0.01	[0.040, 0.321]	0.88	1.29	1.08	16	
Epithelium	14	0.38	0.70	[-0.150, 0.215]	1.05	1.51	1.23	15	
Fully healed	-	-	-	-	0.86	1.72	1.26	17	

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Supplemental Table S2. Min, max, and mean of wound measurements (frontal and sagittal length, cranial and caudal depth) and days disbudded for each tissue type. Mean, SE, and 95% CI by treatment and week for MNT and ADG.

Tissue types	Sagittal length			Frontal length			Cranial depth			Caudal depth			Days disbudded		
	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean
Attached necrotic	17.44	32.85	24.06	14.56	31.23	23.91	0.27	2.96	1.77	0.29	2.49	1.21	2	13	6
Detaching necrotic	14.86	33.01	23.75	10.45	29.37	23.21	0.38	5.10	2.71	0.13	4.88	2.22	7	143	57
Exudate	6.73	23.81	17.62	10.67	23.83	16.65	0.00	5.34	2.58	0.00	4.53	1.83	30	164	96
Granulation	3.56	22.81	11.88	8.97	23.22	15.28	0.00	3.24	0.75	0.00	4.31	0.85	30	180	97
Crust	3.56	20.27	10.83	7.00	22.42	14.67	0.00	3.12	0.61	0.00	4.15	0.69	33	200	107
Epithelium	3.21	16.09	6.22	6.23	30.82	14.21	0.00	0.62	0.05	0.00	0.62	0.05	44	229	121
Fully healed	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	61	218	121

Treatment	Week	ADG wk 1-6			Horn bud MNT			Flank MNT		
		Mean	SE	CI	Mean	SE	CI	Mean	SE	CI
Paste disbudded	1	0.47	0.07	[0.39, 0.55]	1.34	0.06	[1.28, 1.40]	2.66	0.32	[2.32, 2.99]
	2	0.48	0.02	[0.46, 0.51]	1.27	0.05	[1.22, 1.32]	3.08	0.37	[2.69, 3.47]
	3	0.72	0.05	[0.67, 0.77]	1.12	0.03	[1.09, 1.15]	2.75	0.35	[2.37, 3.12]
	4	0.68	0.03	[0.65, 0.71]	1.14	0.04	[1.10, 1.17]	2.92	0.32	[2.58, 3.25]
	5	0.75	0.04	[0.71, 0.79]	1.10	0.04	[1.07, 1.14]	2.34	0.26	[2.05, 2.62]
	6	0.73	0.06	[0.67, 0.80]	1.16	0.04	[1.13, 1.20]	2.95	0.32	[2.62, 3.29]
Control	1	0.50	0.08	[0.41, 0.59]	1.58	0.07	[1.51, 1.65]	3.16	0.54	[2.58, 3.74]
	2	0.46	0.04	[0.41, 0.51]	1.55	0.07	[1.47, 1.62]	2.55	0.33	[2.20, 2.91]
	3	0.77	0.10	[0.66, 0.87]	1.38	0.06	[1.32, 1.43]	2.72	0.35	[2.35, 3.10]
	4	0.70	0.03	[0.67, 0.73]	1.43	0.05	[1.38, 1.48]	2.51	0.29	[2.21, 2.82]
	5	0.83	0.05	[0.77, 0.88]	1.41	0.05	[1.35, 1.46]	3.16	0.41	[2.72, 3.60]
	6	0.66	0.06	[0.60, 0.73]	1.47	0.05	[1.41, 1.52]	3.42	0.42	[2.96, 3.89]